

Symbolic Reform or Systemic Change? A Policy Process Analysis of Australia's National Clothing Product Stewardship Scheme

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Abstract

The National Clothing Product Stewardship Scheme (NCPSS), launched in 2023, represents Australia's first coordinated attempt to address textile waste through extended producer responsibility (EPR) and *circular economy* principles. While the scheme signals progress in recognising fashion's environmental impacts, questions remain about whether it constitutes systemic reform or primarily symbolic action. This paper applies policy process analysis to examine the dynamics that shaped the NCPSS, drawing on frameworks of *incrementalism*, policy learning, and advocacy coalitions. It evaluates how government, industry, and civil society actors interacted to define the problem of textile waste, and how political incentives, institutional constraints, and competing narratives influenced policy outcomes. Evidence from parliamentary inquiries, government reports, and industry submissions reveals a process characterised by fragmented governance, limited federal leadership, and reliance on voluntary industry mechanisms. The analysis highlights a persistent tension between co-regulation and accountability, raising concerns about whether the NCPSS can deliver measurable reductions in textile waste or merely legitimise existing practices. Ultimately, the study argues that embedding enforceable standards, robust data systems, and independent oversight will be essential if the scheme is to move beyond symbolic reform toward systemic change aligned with Australia's *circular economy* and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Keywords: Textile Waste; National Clothing Product Stewardship Scheme (NCPSS); Policy Process Analysis; Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR); Circular Economy (CE); Sustainable Consumption and Production (SCP); Governance; Incrementalism; Advocacy Coalitions; Policy Learning; Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); Australia.

Acronyms:

ACF	Advocacy Coalition Framework
AFC	Australian Fashion Council
BIC	Building Innovative Capability
CE	Circular Economy
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
GFC	Global Financial Crisis
NACRO	National Association of Charitable Recycling Organisations
NCPSS	National Clothing Product Stewardship Scheme
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
SAC	Sustainable Apparel Coalition
SCSS	Seamless Clothing Stewardship Scheme
SRU	Sustainable Resource Use
TFIA	Council of Textile and Fashion Industries of Australia
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WRAP	Waste and Resources Action Programme

Introduction:

The textile industry in Australia has long been marked by governance gaps and policy neglect. Domestic production declined sharply prior to the Global Financial Crisis (GFC), leaving brands increasingly reliant on offshore supply chains supported by trade agreements and tariff reductions (Delaney et al., 2012). Government interventions such as the Rudd Labor Government's *Building Innovative Capability* (BIC) scheme (2009) offered only limited relief, and were later superseded by the Abbott Government's *Textile, Clothing and Footwear Investment and Innovation Programs Amendment Bill* (2014). Rather than fostering resilience, these shifts entrenched import dependency, driving a steady inflow of cheap apparel and an escalating outflow of textile waste.

The entry of international fast fashion retailers such as Topshop (2009), Zara (2011), and H&M (2014) accelerated these dynamics, amplifying overconsumption and highlighting systemic regulatory failures. Governance inquiries during this period documented widespread corporate social responsibility (CSR) shortcomings and human rights violations, attributing them to inadequate regulatory frameworks and weak government oversight (Delaney et al., 2012). Such findings raise critical questions: were these outcomes the result of political instability, deliberate agendas, or the prioritisation of economic growth over sustainability?

Industry actors responded unevenly. The *Council of Textile and Fashion Industries of Australia* (TFIA), though now defunct, warned as early as 2010 that “100 million units of stock are going to waste each year—some of which are intentionally destroyed by retailers before charities can even get a look in” (Simmons, 2010). Their concerns went largely unheeded, though they foreshadowed contemporary debates on fast fashion waste. In 2018, the *Australian Fashion Council* (AFC) was established through a merger of the TFIA and the *Australia Fashion Chamber*, positioning itself as the industry's peak body. Framing itself as a policy community, the AFC now seeks to “effectively champion an innovative, resilient and sustainable legacy for the industry.”

This historical backdrop highlights the conditions under which textile waste emerged as a neglected but urgent policy problem. The following analysis examines how the *National Clothing Product Stewardship Scheme* (NCPSS) has been shaped by these dynamics, and whether it represents a genuine policy innovation or a displacement of responsibility onto industry. By drawing on policy process frameworks, this paper interrogates how problem definition, advocacy coalitions, and governance capacity influence Australia's ability to align textile waste management with *circular economy* and sustainability goals.

The Emergence of the NCPSS: From Agenda-Setting to Design:

The 2021 *Industry Clothing Textiles Waste Roundtable and Exhibition*, convened by then Environment Minister Sussan Ley, marked a pivotal moment in elevating textile waste onto the national policy agenda (QUT Design Lab, 2021). Bringing together coalition groups, industry stakeholders, and research organisations—including the *Circular Centre*, *Queensland University of Technology*, *Charitable Recycling Australia* (NACRO), *SCRgroup*, and major retailers such as the *Kmart Group*—the event exemplified how policy networks can shape agenda-setting through concentrated stakeholder mobilisation. While some critics viewed the initiative as a politically expedient attempt to enhance the Minister’s public profile within a “glamorous” sector, its substantive outcome was the addition of clothing textiles to the *Minister’s Product Stewardship Priority List (2021–2022)*.

This agenda-setting milestone was followed by federal government funding to develop the NCPSS, led by the *Australian Fashion Council*. The NCPSS positions itself as a “world-class initiative” designed to improve design, recovery, reuse, and recycling, offering a roadmap to circularity in Australia by 2030 (AFC, 2023). The consortium, which includes *Sustainable Resource Use* (SRU) and the *Waste and Resources Action Programme* (WRAP), has acted as a coalition of policy entrepreneurs. Their outputs, such as the *Global Scan Report (2023)* and *Clothing Data Report (2023)*, provide an evidence base intended to guide the scheme’s architecture.

Developed through a largely positivist policy approach, the NCPSS sets milestones aligned with rational decision-making and future-oriented planning, including the ambitious aim of achieving a net-zero fashion and textile industry by 2050. This framing reflects a mission-oriented orientation: recognising the magnitude of the global textile waste crisis and situating reform as both urgent and systemic. By institutionalising foundation members and fostering cross-sector collaboration, the scheme aspires to mitigate barriers to effective reform, reduce fragmentation, and reshape the industry’s trajectory towards circularity.

Framing the NCPSS through Policy Process Theories:

The *Building Innovative Capability* (BIC) scheme and the *Textile, Clothing and Footwear Investment and Innovation Programs Amendment Bill* may have been developed through rationalist assumptions. However, it is more likely that *bounded rationality* shaped these policies, driving an intention to invest in long-term growth within the constraints of limited information and political feasibility (OECD, 2009). Policymaking through non-radical steps—what Lindblom described as *incrementalism*—relied on economic drivers alone,

highlighting policy problems but entrenching the status quo as the central concept guiding decisions (Atkinson, 2011). This *incrementalism* contributed to unsustainable growth within both the industry and the environment.

Public and private sector calls for an end to the environmental impacts of textile waste created a pressing problem stream (Taylor, 2021). Acknowledging this challenge at a time when radical policymaking was required, the federal government instead turned to industry to devise a solution (Cairney, 2019). The consortium behind the NCPSS acted as policy entrepreneurs, described by Althaus et al. (2023, p. 66) as “entrepreneurs and experts [who] contribute to deliberations,” enabling the NCPSS policy stream to propose sector-wide responses.

The 2021 change in federal government—from the presiding Coalition to the current Labor government—did not close the political stream; rather, momentum towards achieving NCPSS milestones has continued to shape outputs. Interest group pressure and the global paradigm for a sustainable and circular fashion industry further ensure the continued “use of persuasion to connect solutions to the beliefs of audiences” (Cairney, 2019, p. 188). Assuming ongoing governmental recognition of fashion waste as a policy priority, and continual calls for regulatory reform by international policy entrepreneurs such as the *United Nations Environment Programme* (UNEP) and the *United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change* (UNFCCC), the conditions for cooperation remain. This convergence sustains the agenda and keeps open a policy window for further reform.

Incrementalism in Practice: The NCPSS through a Bounded Rationality Lens

Federal government policymakers have historically been seen as “muddling through” industry reforms rather than pursuing comprehensive strategies. The development of the *National Clothing Product Stewardship Scheme* (NCPSS) reflects this dynamic, where policy change emerges incrementally rather than through radical transformation. As Allen (2020) observes, policy analysis is best understood through the “process-relevant actors and factors that give rise to policy change vis-à-vis the policy status quo” (p. 117). He further notes that policy process is “central to analysing policy change” and that the analytical space “simultaneously determines the actors and factors that will be considered in the analysis and the relationships between the two” (Allen, 2020, p. 120). *Incrementalism*, by offering the broadest analytical space for examining such shifts, frames the establishment of the NCPSS as the product of interactions between policy problems, ideas, and the expertise of embedded actors.

Relationships within the NCPSS policy network—particularly between the AFC and domestic brands—are likely to encounter opposition during implementation. As Allen (2020) argues, “feedback from policy learning” can prompt small-scale adjustments, reinforcing *incrementalism* as an ongoing process. Coalition advocates such as the *Sustainable Apparel Coalition* (SAC) also influence these dynamics, strengthening the legitimacy of reform efforts. The OECD (2013) highlights that “the position of a network is a significant predictor of whether social movement organisations are perceived to be effective” (p. 15), suggesting that the NCPSS’s international affiliations bolster its authority.

This epistemic community of industry leaders, charities, and international partners reflects the conditions of the *Advocacy Coalition Framework* (ACF), where policy subsystems are shaped by shared beliefs and long-term strategies (Cairney, 2019). The gradual nature of NCPSS milestones illustrates incremental decision-making: research outputs and milestone reports allow time to assimilate findings and diffuse them across the industry. However, early reforms may be constrained by entrenched unsustainable practices and cognitive biases within the sector. As Cairney (2020) notes, policymakers often operate with “uncertain and limited information” (p. 55), undermining the possibility of comprehensive rationality. These constraints highlight why the NCPSS has developed as a stepwise process of adaptation and learning, rather than a transformative break with the past.

Case Studies in Policy Design and Implementation:

Global Scan Report: Insights into Global Policy Models

The *Global Scan Report*, released as Milestone 1.4 of the NCPSS, provides a critical overview of international approaches to clothing circularity and their relevance to Australia’s policy landscape. The report categorises global initiatives into four types: (1) voluntary NGO initiatives without regulatory backing, (2) pilot studies, (3) voluntary industry-led schemes, and (4) government-regulated systems with either voluntary, hybrid, or mandatory requirements. These typologies illustrate the spectrum of governance mechanisms shaping textile waste policy, from grassroots advocacy through to enforceable regulation.

The analysis highlights a key weakness of unregulated NGO initiatives: while they promote *circular economy* (CE) principles and foster experimentation, their legitimacy and capacity for industry-wide transformation are limited without government endorsement. In the context of the NCPSS, this underscores the importance of epistemic learning—whereby policymakers draw on independent initiatives to identify emerging issues—while recognising that without institutional support, their influence remains marginal.

Pilot studies and voluntary industry schemes represent another tier of *incrementalism*, allowing for experimentation and consensus-building but often delaying systemic reform. As the report notes, these approaches risk normalising gradualism, sending weak signals to public and private actors about the urgency of transitioning to circular systems. This aligns with Lindblom’s concept of “muddling through,” where small adjustments substitute for structural change, reinforcing the persistence of the status quo.

By contrast, the *Global Scan Report* positions government-regulated schemes as the most effective mechanism for driving durable change. Through enforceable targets and compliance frameworks, regulation provides a stronger basis for accountability and industry-wide transformation. Importantly, the report suggests that regulation works most effectively when coupled with citizen engagement—through both special interest groups and public interest advocates—ensuring democratic legitimacy alongside technical rigour.

Taken together, the *Global Scan Report* reflects a policy learning process that resonates with *bounded rationality* and *incrementalism*. It demonstrates how international precedents can inform Australian reforms but also signals that without regulatory authority and political will, the NCPSS risks replicating the shortcomings of voluntary initiatives. The case study therefore illustrates both the opportunities and constraints of policy diffusion in shaping Australia’s circular fashion future.

Comparative Lessons: France’s Anti-Waste and Circular Economy Law (AGEC)

The French *Anti-Waste and Circular Economy Law (AGEC)*, adopted in February 2020, represents one of the most ambitious attempts at legislating systemic change in the textile sector. Reported by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation as an “ambitious law for systems change” (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2021), the AGECE consists of 130 articles that embed compulsory product stewardship (PS) and extended producer responsibility (EPR) into national governance structures. Evidence suggests that such mandatory frameworks “can achieve more consistency for industry within their jurisdiction than countries that have not enacted sector-wide schemes,” since they enforce centralised accountability measures while leaving industries flexibility in determining how to achieve compliance (NCPSS, 2023).

Although the adoption of the AGECE appeared rapid, its foundations were established earlier through the *Circular Economy Roadmap (2017)*, which underwent an extensive public consultation process before the law’s finalisation in 2020. This sequencing illustrates how consultation and iterative design are essential in avoiding policy obsolescence. As noted in the NCPSS evaluation, “the success of mandatory schemes is dependent on their design. Mandatory schemes run the risk of being not fit-for-purpose or outdated in instances where

they do not consult relevant industry stakeholders during their design, or when regular review periods are not in-built” (NCPSS, 2023).

The French model underscores both the advantages and risks of mandatory schemes. On one hand, statutory regulation establishes enforceable obligations and sends a strong signal of government commitment, creating a stable foundation for systemic reform. On the other, without careful consultation and adaptive review mechanisms, such schemes risk being rigid and ineffective. In contrast, voluntary or semi-voluntary schemes, such as the NCPSS, allow for industry-led adoption and collaboration through best practice, but often lack enforceability and consistency.

By examining the AGEC alongside the NCPSS, it becomes clear that while France has advanced towards mandatory regulation in the 2020s, Australia continues to rely on incremental, voluntary approaches. This divergence highlights a broader global trend: voluntary schemes dominated the early 2000s and 2010s, but the current decade is witnessing growing momentum toward mandatory regulation for textiles to accelerate sustainability and circularity. For the NCPSS, the French case demonstrates the potential benefits of embedding statutory authority and adaptive review mechanisms into its design, thereby transforming what might otherwise remain symbolic reform into genuine systemic change.

Clothing Data Report: Addressing Evidence Gaps and Industry Commitments

The *Clothing Data Report* (2023), released as part of the NCPSS Milestone 1.4, highlights the centrality of evidence-building in steering Australia’s transition toward a circular textile economy. By working alongside industry actors and subgroups, the scheme has sought to foster deeper social learning and shared understanding of current practices. Yet the report simultaneously underscores the limitations of Australia’s existing knowledge base, noting that “large data gaps make it difficult to see problems clearly” (Esty & Rushing, 2007). Such deficits raise a critical policy question: do voids in information inevitably translate into voids in policy? Without a comprehensive evidence base, policymaking risks being shaped by partial or fragmented understandings, weakening the capacity for systemic reform.

In response, the NCPSS frames its role as not merely technical but epistemic, seeking to enhance policy impact by addressing these knowledge deficits. Consistent with Althaus et al.’s (2023, p. 32) emphasis on identifying gaps as a precondition for good practice, the NCPSS has mapped six key data voids while outlining five priority areas for further research. This evidence-driven orientation positions the scheme as a policy entrepreneur in its own right, providing the analytic foundation needed to legitimise incremental decisions and strengthen the credibility of the broader *circular economy* agenda.

The political salience of the *Clothing Data Report* was further amplified in June 2023, when several major retailers—including Big W, David Jones, Lorna Jane, Rip Curl, R.M. Williams, and The Iconic—committed \$100,000 each to support the scheme’s transition phase. These contributions, structured around initial funding and a proposed 4-cent-per-garment levy, signal growing industry buy-in. According to *Ragtrader*, if 60% of the market by volume were to participate, a funding pool of \$36 million could be mobilised annually, with activities projected to divert 60% of end-of-life clothing from landfill by 2027 (Kelly, 2023).

The conditionality of these commitments—“progress within one year or face regulation”—illustrates the interplay of voluntary and coercive instruments in the current policy landscape. At this juncture, the future of the NCPSS hinges not only on the technical task of closing data gaps but also on the willingness of designers, brands, and retailers to embed circularity into their business models. As such, the *Clothing Data Report* exemplifies the incremental but critical process of evidence-building, agenda-setting, and coalition-building that will determine whether the scheme evolves into systemic reform or remains symbolic. In this sense, the report serves as both a diagnostic tool and a political litmus test, revealing how the success of the NCPSS will ultimately depend on whether voluntary commitments can transition into enforceable and enduring mechanisms of change.

Seamless Implementation as a Test of Systemic Reform

Launched in June 2023, the *Seamless Clothing Stewardship Scheme* (SCSS) was presented as “changing the way we design, consume and recycle clothing” (NCPSS, 2023). Spearheaded by the *Australian Fashion Council* in collaboration with a multi-stakeholder consortium, *Seamless* represents the first industry-wide attempt to operationalise the principles of circularity through coordinated design reform, innovation, citizen engagement, and high-value recycling. While celebrated as “a great first step” (Terzon, 2023), the scheme has already been framed by policymakers as a transitional measure, with recognition that a mandatory framework is likely inevitable.

This trajectory was underscored by Environment Minister Tanya Plibersek’s one-year ultimatum to industry: “This can be an industry-led approach ... or I’ll do it” (Ragtrader, 2023). The Minister’s Priority List (2022–23) sets out three ongoing expectations: (1) reducing clothing sent to landfill by prioritising longevity, reuse, and recyclability; (2) establishing a national stewardship scheme for end-of-life textiles across the full value chain; and (3) reducing lifecycle impacts through product design improvements. These priorities, while progressing, remain contingent on demonstrable industry leadership.

The implementation of *Seamless* illustrates both the promise and the fragility of incremental reform. Early phases rely on collaboration among foundation members, with

each organisation contributing to the 12-month transition period. The scheme is expected to evolve iteratively, with policies altered, adjusted, and negotiated in response to feedback. In practice, this means embedding learning-by-doing, tolerating trial and error, and recalibrating approaches to reflect gaps and challenges.

Key to its success is not only technical reform—such as incentivising durable and recyclable design, expanding collection systems, and fostering circular business models—but also shifts in citizen behaviour. National education campaigns and improved access to repair, care, and recycling services are intended to extend garment lifespans and alter consumption norms. Yet obstacles are likely, particularly in overcoming entrenched fast fashion habits and coordinating diverse industry actors.

Ultimately, *Seamless* tests whether voluntary, industry-led stewardship can achieve systemic change in the absence of statutory compulsion. It embodies the incrementalism identified throughout the NCPSS: gradual progress toward circularity, negotiated compromises, and reliance on advocacy coalitions to sustain momentum. Whether this amounts to systemic reform or symbolic transition will depend on the scheme's ability to convert voluntary commitments into measurable outcomes before government intervention becomes unavoidable.

Case Study Synthesis: Lessons for Australian Policy

The four case studies—the *Global Scan Report*, France's *Anti-Waste and Circular Economy Law (AGEC)*, the *Clothing Data Report*, and the launch of the *Seamless Scheme*—collectively illustrate the interplay between voluntary and mandatory approaches, as well as the incremental nature of policy development in the textile sector. The *Global Scan* highlights the limitations of voluntary initiatives and the relative strength of government-backed schemes, emphasising the importance of regulation in securing legitimacy and industry-wide change. The French AGECE provides a compelling example of how statutory frameworks can embed extended producer responsibility and product stewardship at scale, but also cautions that without consultation and adaptive review, mandatory schemes risk rigidity. By contrast, the *Clothing Data Report* underscores the persistent evidence gaps in Australia's textile system and the reliance on voluntary commitments from industry actors, reinforcing the challenges of building systemic reform on an incremental foundation.

Taken together, these cases reveal a consistent tension: voluntary schemes encourage innovation and collaboration but lack enforceability, while mandatory schemes provide accountability but require careful design to remain effective over time. For the NCPSS, this comparative analysis signals both the opportunities and vulnerabilities of its current trajectory. Without enforceable standards, the NCPSS risks replicating the

shortcomings of past voluntary initiatives; yet, with incremental progress, coalition building, and data-driven policy learning, it has the potential to lay the groundwork for systemic reform. This synthesis positions the *Seamless Scheme* as the critical test of whether Australia's incremental approach can deliver meaningful transformation or remain symbolic in the face of global momentum towards mandatory regulation.

Conclusion: Incremental Pathways to Seamless Change

The launch of the *Seamless Clothing Stewardship Scheme* (SCSS) in June 2023 was framed as “changing the way we design, consume and recycle clothing” (NCPSS, 2023). Spearheaded by the AFC and its consortium partners, *Seamless* positions itself as the first industry-wide attempt to embed circularity in Australia's fashion sector. Its stated ambition is to transform outdated business models, drive innovation, shift consumer behaviour, and promote high-value recycling. While welcomed as “a great first step” (Terzon, 2023), the scheme is widely regarded as transitional, with policymakers and stakeholders acknowledging that a mandatory framework is likely inevitable.

The Minister's Priority List (2022–23) has yet to be updated, with actions still reflecting three core objectives: (1) reducing the volume of clothing sent to landfill by prioritising durability, reuse, and recyclability by 2025; (2) designing a national product stewardship scheme for end-of-life textiles, including uniforms and workwear, across the full value chain; and (3) reducing lifecycle impacts of clothing through design improvements related to durability, reparability, and recyclability by 2025. These commitments remain marked as “progressing” or “ongoing,” yet their credibility will ultimately depend on demonstrable industry action. As *Seamless* enters its transition phase, success will hinge on the ability of foundation members to adapt, negotiate, and collaborate, with iterative policy adjustment and “learning by doing” shaping the scheme's trajectory.

As the scheme and subsequent policies are progressively introduced, approaches will need to be continually refined rather than drawn from outdated frameworks. Continuous collaboration between foundation members is imperative in the initial stages, with “each organisation to play an important part in the 12-month transition phase while *Seamless* is established.” This process reflects a model of trial, error, and adaptation, where incremental reforms are tested and recalibrated in response to emerging challenges.

Policy gaps are likely to emerge but can be addressed through action across the entire value chain—from design and production to use, reuse, collection, and recycling. The scheme's stated priorities of incentivising durable and recyclable design, fostering circular business models, and expanding collection and recycling infrastructure will demand

coordinated effort from multiple industry actors nationwide. Transition may be gradual, but through compromise and iterative reform, systemic barriers can be reduced.

Equally critical is citizen engagement. Shifting consumer behaviour in clothing acquisition, use, care, and disposal will require national and regional education campaigns, as well as accessible infrastructure and services that extend garment lifespans. While obstacles are likely, leveraging advocacy coalitions, policy entrepreneurs, and community networks will help disseminate knowledge and build momentum for change.

Looking ahead, the envisioned future of Australia's textile sector is one where "the wardrobe of the future will represent responsible stewardship and citizenship from clothing design and production, through to consumption and recirculation." Achieving this vision will depend on incremental but sustained reform, with 2030 wardrobes projected to contain fewer garments—each designed for longevity, produced from renewable fibres, and embedded within a truly circular system.

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